

Research on factors affecting the decision to apply the SMART model in office work planning at Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company

Nguyen Thi Tuyen, Nguyen Huu Minh*

School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry

Email: nghuuminh1403@gmail.com

Abstract : *In the context of increasing competitive pressure and the demand for improved office management efficiency, the application of modern planning methods has become an essential requirement for Vietnamese enterprises. The reality at Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company shows that although the SMART model has been introduced and applied experimentally, the level of implementation is uneven among departments, the achieved efficiency is not stable, and employees' awareness of the model is still different. The objective of this study is to identify and measure the factors influencing the decision to apply the SMART model in office work planning within the enterprise. The survey results show that there are 5 main factors that positively affect the decision to apply SMART, including: (1) Awareness of the SMART model, (2) Leadership support, (3) Planning ability, (4) Organizational environment and culture, and (5) Resources and support means. The survey collected 240 votes, of which 215 were valid. The valid votes will be entered into SPSS 20 software for research. The research findings provide a foundation for enterprises to develop solutions that enhance the effectiveness of applying the SMART model in the future.*

Keywords: SMART modul; office; office work planning.

1. Introduction

Globalization and the Industrial Revolution 4.0 have posed major challenges for organizations in improving management efficiency and optimizing work productivity. Office management is a topic that has not been widely studied and paid attention to in Vietnam, although the office is considered the common operating platform of every organization. These activities have their own characteristics and properties, requiring appropriate tools and methods for measuring performance (Tuyn, 2025). Office work planning, as one of the core functions of management, helps businesses clearly define goals, allocate resources appropriately and ensure activities are on track. (Robbins & Coulter, 1995). Minh (2025) shows that office performance plays an important mediating role between organizational factors and the overall performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. Effective planning not only promotes cohesion and coordination among functional units but also plays a key role in enhancing the organization's competitiveness in the market.

One of the effective goal planning support tools is the SMART model, proposed by Doran (1981) with 5 criteria: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant và Time-bound. Studies by Armstrong (2009); Latham (1990) shows that this model helps clarify goals, increase the ability to measure results, and improve employee motivation. However, applying SMART in practice does not always achieve maximum efficiency, because it depends on many factors such as employee awareness, leadership support, planning ability, organizational environment and culture, as well as resources and support means. In the context of strong development of the digital economy and the trend of international integration in recent years, more and more businesses in Vietnam are focusing on implementing modern management methods as a solution to improve operational efficiency.. However, surveys and reports from many organizations show that planning in many businesses is still formal and lacks specific measurement criteria, leading to slow progress or failure to meet requirements in implementing goals. Many agencies and units still apply traditional goal setting methods, not fully exploiting the benefits of tools such as the SMART model, resulting in low efficiency in work coordination and resource optimization. In addition, employees' understanding of modern planning tools is uneven, while support resources from leaders and the management infrastructure system are still inadequate.

From this reality, the study of factors affecting the decision to apply the SMART model in office work planning becomes urgent, in order to provide scientific evidence and feasible solutions to improve the effectiveness of goal management in the current context of Vietnam.

2. Theoretical basis and research overview

2.1. Office Concept

In the modern context, the concept of office is not only associated with physical space but also extends to factors of organizational structure, working methods, supporting technology and digital working environment. According to the 1992 Vietnamese Dictionary, office is the department in charge of official documents and administrative papers in an agency or unit. This concept identifies the office with the clerical department of an agency or unit. According to Nguyen Thanh Do (Độ, 2005), The concept of "Office" is understood from many different perspectives. In a broad sense: An office is a comprehensive working apparatus that directly supports the management of an agency or unit. According to this concept, for general authorities and large-scale organizations, the office is established as a separate department, while in small units, the office function is often undertaken by the general administrative department. In a narrow sense: An office is the working headquarters of an agency or unit, and is the place for internal and external communication of that agency or unit. The authors use the most general understanding of Tuyen and Minh (2025) (Tuyền, 2025): The office is a department that performs internal and external administrative functions as a center for connecting, receiving, processing, and transmitting information with the aim of promoting the operational efficiency of agencies, organizations, and businesses.

2.2. Office work planning

Office work planning is the process of determining in advance the tasks to be performed, at the same time establishing specific goals, allocating resources, time and organization methods appropriately to ensure efficiency, progress and conformity with the overall goals of the organization. According to Thanh (2009), Office planning is the activity of "planning administrative and office activities to ensure that work is performed correctly, on time and with high efficiency". In the current working context, when work pressure increases and the need to process information at high speed becomes urgent, work planning becomes essential to improve work efficiency, avoid overlap, lack of resources, and help the office operate more smoothly and professionally.

2.3. Research overview

The SMART model was first introduced by Doran (Doran, 1981) with 5 criteria: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound, to help organizations set clear, specific, and measurable goals. Latham's research (Latham, 1990) has demonstrated that applying SMART not only increases the likelihood of goal completion, but also significantly improves employee motivation and performance. Armstrong (2009) also emphasizes the importance of SMART in performance management, as it allows managers and employees to control progress and results in a transparent and systematic way. Many studies have studied the factors that influence the decision to apply modern planning methods such as SMART. Bass and Avolio (1994) argues that leadership support is a key factor in encouraging employees to adopt new management tools, especially in the early stages of implementation. Robbins and Coulter (2021) (Robbins & Coulter, 1995) recognized that individual planning abilities play a direct role in ensuring that SMART goals are effectively achieved. Cameron (2011) indicates that a supportive organizational culture and environment that encourages innovation will increase the adoption and use of modern management models. Besides, Barney (1991) and Davis (1989) emphasized the role of resources and support means, considering this a necessary condition to ensure success in implementation. Similarly, research by Latham (2004) on goal setting emphasizes that the SMART criteria can be flexibly applied in many organizational contexts, from the public to the

private sector, as long as there are appropriate adjustments to suit the specific culture and strategy of the organization.

In Vietnam, there are not many in-depth studies on the application of SMART in office planning, but some works have mentioned related factors. Van (Vân, 2024) analyzed the current state of planning in Vietnamese enterprises, showing that many units still lack specific measurement criteria and have not focused on training employees on modern planning tools. Some other authors such as Thuy et al (Thùy et al., 2019) also shows that a positive working environment, appropriate incentive mechanisms and technological support will enhance the effectiveness of applying target management models.

Synthesizing domestic and foreign studies shows that the application of the SMART model is affected by many factors, which can be divided into five main groups: (1) Awareness of the SMART model, (2) Leadership support, (3) Planning ability, (4) Organizational environment and culture, and (5) Resources and support means. This is an important theoretical basis for building a research and testing model in the current practical context..

3. Research method

The study surveyed 240 officers and employees of Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company from April 2025 to June 2025 on factors affecting the application of the SMART model in office planning at Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company. The survey results obtained 240 votes, of which 215 were valid.

With the scale of "factors affecting the application of the SMART model in office planning", the author extracted 05 factors. (1) Awareness of the SMART model; (2) Support from leaders; (3) Planning ability; (4) Organizational environment and culture; (5) Resources and planning means. On that basis, the author built indicators to measure the influence of factors on the application of the SMART model in office planning. These observed variables use a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". The 24 observed variables are presented in the table below

Table 1. Suggested scale

Serial	Scale	Symbol	Suggested observation variables
1	Awareness of the SMART model	NT1	I understand the 5 criteria of the SMART model
		NT2	I believe that the SMART model helps to define goals more clearly
		NT3	I think that SMART makes it easier to evaluate work progress and results
		NT4	I find that SMART is suitable for the specific nature of office work at the company
		NT5	I believe that SMART helps to improve team coordination efficiency
		NT6	I have been provided with full information about the SMART model
2	Leadership Support	LD1	Leaders encourage the application of the SMART model

		LD2	Leaders provide clear guidance when implementing the SMART model
		LD3	Leaders allocate resources to support the application of the SMART model
		LD4	Leaders regularly monitor and provide feedback on results according to the SMART criteria
		LD5	Leaders acknowledge and encourage when goals are achieved
3	Planning Ability	KH1	I am able to clearly define work goals
		KH2	I am able to allocate time and work reasonably
		KH3	I am able to forecast and handle risks when planning
		KH4	I am able to adjust plans when situations change
4	Organizational Culture and Environment	MT1	The company culture encourages transparency and information sharing
		MT2	Departments collaborate effectively to achieve common goals.
		MT3	The company emphasizes setting clear goals and measuring results
		MT4	The company has an effective feedback and evaluation mechanism
5	Resources and Planning Means	NL1	The company provides software and support tools
		NL2	The company ensures sufficient human resources for the implementation of the SMART model
		NL3	The company ensures sufficient budget for SMART training activities.
		NL4	Employees are trained in the necessary skills to apply SMART
		NL5	Detailed guidance documents on the application of SMART are available

(Source: Proposed by the author group)

The author used the non-probability purposive sampling method (Judgement Sampling). The study was conducted on 240 employees working at Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company. Through the collection process, the author group received 240 survey forms, of which 215 valid forms were included in the analysis. This sample number is considered valid according to Hair

recommendations (Hair, 2011), in which the number of samples is 5 times the number of observed variables ($24 * 5 = 120$ samples). Finally, to test the level of suitability, the author used SPSS 20 software to evaluate the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, KMO coefficient and the level of convergence through EFA assessment (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023). The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of each observed variable must be greater than 0.3 to be considered valid. For EFA assessment, factor loading coefficients greater than 0.5 are considered statistically significant.

4. Research results

4.1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability assessment

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient has a value varying in the range [0,1]. Accordingly, a scale is considered to be of good quality when it satisfies the following two conditions: (1) The overall Cronbach's Alpha coefficient > 0.7 and (2) The total item correlation coefficient > 0.3 . In case the variables have a total item correlation coefficient < 0.3 , they are considered as garbage variables and are removed from the scale. The results of the Cronbach's Alpha reliability test of the groups of variables are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha results - Assessing the reliability of the scale

Variable	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item – Total Correlation)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted)
Awareness of SMART model – Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.932				
NT1	18,40	24,98	0,866	0,910
NT2	18,69	26,67	0,793	0,920
NT3	18,33	26,07	0,777	0,922
NT4	18,80	26,13	0,769	0,923
NT5	18,77	26,56	0,776	0,922
NT6	18,68	26,00	0,818	0,917
Leadership Support - Cronbach's Alpha = 0.864				
LD1	14,35	10,79	0,724	0,826
LD2	14,54	10,90	0,618	0,855
LD3	14,23	11,62	0,622	0,851
LD4	14,45	10,58	0,789	0,810
LD5	14,28	10,93	0,682	0,836
Planning Ability – Cronbach Alpha Coefficient = 0.930				
KH1	9,79	11,91	0,853	0,903
KH2	9,72	11,96	0,791	0,924

KH3	9,82	11,95	0,834	0,909
KH4	9,77	11,46	0,867	0,898
Organizational culture and environment – Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.910				
MT1	10,08	9,88	0,822	0,874
MT2	9,91	10,25	0,745	0,901
MT3	9,96	9,62	0,814	0,877
MT4	10,05	9,97	0,803	0,881
Resources and planning means – Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.908				
NL1	13,75	15,17	0,804	0,880
NL2	13,67	15,62	0,734	0,895
NL3	13,65	14,96	0,795	0,882
NL4	13,75	15,27	0,770	0,887
NL5	13,82	15,79	0,737	0,894
Decision to apply SMART model – Cronbach Alpha coefficient = 0.907				
QD1	14,13	16,31	0,788	0,882
QD2	14,01	17,31	0,729	0,894
QD3	14,11	16,96	0,749	0,890
QD4	13,95	15,83	0,777	0,884
QD5	14,07	16,19	0,790	0,881

(Source: Proposed by the author group)

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

After testing the reliability of the scale using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the evaluated scales continued to be put into exploratory factor analysis EFA. The test results are presented in Table 3 and Table 4 below.

Table 3. KMO coefficient and extracted variance

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,835
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3620,635
	df	276
	Sig.	0,000

(Source: Proposed by the author group)

The EFA analysis results have KMO index = 0.835 > 0.5 and Sig. Bartlett's Test value = 0.000 < 0.05, so EFA exploratory factor analysis is appropriate. There are 5 factors extracted with Eigenvalue criterion greater than 1 and total extracted variance is 74.901%. Thus, 5 extracted factors explain 74.901% of the variation in data. In addition, all observed variables converge into 5 factor groups and have loading factor > 0.5 (Table 4). This is consistent with the recommendation of Hair et al. (2006)

Table 4. Results of the rotated matrix table of factors

Variable	Awareness of SMART model	Leadership Support	Planning Ability	Organizational culture and environment	Decision to apply SMART model
NT1	0,909				
NT6	0,876				
NT2	0,860				
NT3	0,844				
NT5	0,843				
NT4	0,838				
NL1		0,873			
NL3		0,869			
NL4		0,856			
NL2		0,833			
NL5		0,831			
KH4			0,915		
KH1			0,909		

KH3			0,897		
KH2			0,879		
LD4				0,872	
LD1				0,830	
LD5				0,804	
LD3				0,758	
LD2				0,744	
MT1					0,893
MT3					0,888
MT4					0,886
MT2					0,839

(Source: Proposed by the author group)

5. Conclude

The study identified five factors that positively influence the decision to apply the SMART model in office work planning, including: awareness of the model, leadership support, planning ability, organizational environment and culture, and resources and support means. The results supplement empirical evidence for the theory of management by objectives and confirm the suitability of the SMART model in the context of Vietnam. The study provides scientific evidence for managers and policy makers to implement appropriate training programs, promote support from leaders, improve working conditions and allocate resources effectively. The main limitation of the study is the narrow scope of the survey, not considering the industry and organizational size. Further studies should expand the scope and methods to increase generality, improve solutions, and improve the effectiveness of applying the SMART model in office work planning at Dai Viet Administrative Technology Joint Stock Company.

REFERENCES

- Armstrong, M. (2009). *Armstrong's handbook of performance management: An evidence-based guide to delivering high performance*. Kogan page publishers.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99-120.
- Cameron, K. S. (2011). Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework. In: John Wiley & Sons.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of research writing and uses of research methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319-340.
- Doran, G. T. (1981). There's a SMART way to write managements's goals and objectives. *Management review*, 70(11).
- Độ, N. T. (2005). *Giáo trình quản trị văn phòng*.
- Hair, J. F. (2011). Multivariate data analysis: An overview. *International encyclopedia of statistical science*, 904-907.
- Latham, G. P. (2004). The motivational benefits of goal-setting. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 18(4), 126-129.
- Latham, L. v. (1990). *A theory of goal setting & task performance*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Minh. (2025). Office activities performance as a mediator between organizational drivers and firm performance: Evidence from Vietnamese SMEs. . *The Economics and Finance Letters*(2), 463-482. <https://doi.org/10.18488/29.v12i3.4265>
- Robbins, S. P., & Coulter, M. (1995). Principles of management. In.
- Tuyển and Minh (2025). XÂY DỰNG THANG ĐO ĐÁNH GIÁ HIỆU QUẢ HOẠT ĐỘNG VĂN PHÒNG. *Tạp chí Khoa học Trường Đại học Thành Đông*.
- Thanh, V. T. K. (2009). *Quản trị hành chính văn phòng*.
- Thùy, L. P., Duy, V. Q., & Lê Thông, P. (2019). Các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hiệu quả hoạt động của các doanh nghiệp tại Việt Nam. *Tạp chí Khoa học Đại học Cần Thơ*, 55, 12-22.
- Vân, N. T. H. (2024). Thực trạng và giải pháp nâng cao hiệu quả thực thi chính sách đầu tư công. *Quản lý nhà nước*(340), 121-126.